

FOURTH ANNUAL ACADEMIC SESSIONS
COLLEGE OF PALLIATIVE MEDICINE
OF SRI LANKA

Programme
and
Abstract Book

Progress and Reflections

Celebrating the past and shaping the future

19-20th September 2025
Gallface Hotel, Colombo
Sri Lanka

FACILITATORS AND BARRIERS IN ACCESSING PALLIATIVE CARE SERVICES IN LOW- AND MIDDLE-INCOME COUNTRIES: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF QUALITATIVE STUDIES

Gunawardana D.S.K.D.¹, Dharmawardhane M.P.¹, Gunawardana M.D.U.B.¹, Fernando U.P.M.², Weerasooriya S.D.³, Maduranga A.³

¹Postgraduate Institute of Medicine, Colombo, ² Sri Jayewardenepura General Hospital, ³ Regional Directorate of Health services, Colombo

*Corresponding Author: dsupidsk@gmail.com

Background: Access to palliative care is a global health priority, yet significant disparities exist, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). Understanding the perspectives of patients and caregivers is essential to improving equitable access. This review synthesizes qualitative evidence on the barriers and facilitators to accessing palliative care services in LMICs.

Methods: A systematic search was conducted in PubMed, Clinical key and Google Scholar for studies published between 2000 and 2025 by two independent reviewers. This was followed by deduplication. The third reviewer intervened in resolving conflicts. Qualitative studies exploring facilitators and barriers to accessing palliative care in LMICs were included. Data were synthesized using thematic synthesis, and quality was assessed using the JBI Critical Appraisal Checklist for Qualitative Research. PROSPERO registration ID is 1109010.

Results: Following deduplication, title and abstract screening of 687 articles and 15 articles were selected for full text review. The included studies spanned LMICs in Asia and Africa, and involved diverse populations including patients, caregivers, healthcare providers, and policymakers. Common barriers included poor referral systems, centralized services, inadequate infrastructure, financial hardship, limited awareness, and cultural stigma. Facilitators involved provider training, positive attitudes, community-based care models, and stakeholder engagement. Studies emphasized the importance of holistic, culturally sensitive approaches and integration of palliative care into primary healthcare. Themes emerged around health system readiness, societal and cultural influences, and individual-level factors. Overall, improving education, decentralizing services, and fostering supportive provider-patient relationships were critical in enhancing accessibility and utilization of palliative care in resource-limited settings.

Conclusion: Access to palliative care in LMICs can be improved by addressing system gaps, raising awareness, decentralizing services, and promoting culturally sensitive, community-based care models.

Key words: Palliative care access, facilitators, barriers, low and middle income countries

